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Impacts and costs of invasive non-native species, including plant pests and pathogens, establishment in heath and moorland habitats.

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Executive summary

Invasive non-native species (INNS) are species introduced into novel environments via direct (e.g., release of unwanted pets) or indirect (e.g., in contaminated soil) human action, and which go on to have a negative ecological, economic, or societal impact. To date, the majority of research into INNS impacts and costs has focused on agriculture and forestry. In this report we look at the evidence and potential impacts of INNS on heath and moorlands. Heath and moorlands are important iconic landscapes in Scotland, with strong cultural connections and are valued for their unique species.

We conducted a semi-systematic literature review to identify research on heath and moorland invasive species impacts. This included search of the published and grey literature for heath and moorland papers on invasive species, and specific searches for known pests and pathogens in heath and moorland plant species. Due to low numbers of papers identified through the initial literature search we also carried out a review of the potential impacts of a decline in host plants in heath and moorlands caused by the plant pests and pathogens.

Final papers included 6 ecology papers, one economics and no social papers. Overall, the number of papers on invasive species in heath and moorlands was limited. Two plant species were identified, as *Rhododendron ponticum* and *Campylopus introflexus*. Hedgehogs were identified as INNS on heath and moorlands in South Uist, but are native to mainland Scotland, and are not expected to encroach on heath and moorland habitats typically. Two fungi of the genus *Phytophthora* (*P. ramorum* and *P. kernoviae*) were identified in conjunction with host *R. ponticum*.

We identified 49 species that are plant pests or pathogens, with a high likelihood of establishing that could be hosted by plant genera occurring at more than 25% cover on Scottish mires and heaths. We describe the potential impacts of decline in heath and moorland vegetation, such as might be expected by INNS invasions of plant pests/pathogens:

- Loss of option value – particularly important for native *Vaccinium*, relative of the blueberry, with potential agricultural value. *Juniperus* populations also have botanical value as one of the few native conifers of Scotland.
- Reduction in production of food, medicine, fibre – although not the main purpose of heath and moorland, food can be produced through grazing, foraging, and honey production. Fibre and medicine is not produced commercially, but may be locally valuable.
- Decline in water quality – due to soil or nutrient run-off, increasing costs of water cleaning.
- Loss of carbon – potentially significant due to high carbon peat soils
- Increased soil erosion – due to loss of root structure. Erosion currently costs Scotland over 31m/year.
- Reduced flood control – leading to potential damage to health, housing, and infrastructure.
- Altered recreation opportunities – due to loss of native species, however some loss of vegetation (e.g., bracken) may improve access in some areas.

Overall research on impacts of INNS on heath and moorlands is limited, including both ecological impacts and socioeconomic impacts. Despite the limited current evidence, we do present the potential impacts of introduction of INNS to heath and moorlands through the possible declines in vegetation and impacts of this decline across provisioning, regulating and cultural services. Future work will expand understanding of potential impacts of INNS in heath and moorland habitats, and create a toolkit for estimating ecological, social, and economic impacts.

Introduction

Invasive non-native species (INNS) are species introduced into novel environments via direct (e.g., release of unwanted pets) or indirect (e.g., in contaminated soil) human action, and which go on to have a negative ecological, economic or societal impact (Mooney, 2001). This can include invasive animals and plants, but also pests and pathogens. INNS have been recognised as one of the leading drivers of biodiversity decline (IPBES, 2019), and control of INNS is a key action within the Scottish Biodiversity Strategy (Scottish Government, 2022a). The damages caused by invasive species can have significant costs, leading to efforts to control invasive species which are often costly themselves (Hanley and Roberts, 2019).

To date, the majority of research into INNS impacts and costs has focused on agriculture and forestry (Haubrock et al., 2021). This is likely due to their impacts on marketed goods, which therefore have a clear and tangible impact. However, INNS have landscape scale impacts, and have the potential to cause damages across habitats. Heath and moorland, have been recognised as habitats under risk from plant pests and pathogens (Mitchell, 2022), and have also had very little attention with regards to invasive species. Here we refer to heaths, heathlands, moors, moorlands, mires and peatlands as heath and moorland throughout. When specific vegetation communities are referred to we include all those communities within Rodwell (1991).

Heath and moorlands are important iconic landscapes in Scotland (Evans et al., 2017), with strong cultural connections (Game and Wildlife Conservation Trust, 2015) and are valued for their unique species (Glenk and Martin-Ortega, 2018). Many heath and moorlands habitats include peat soils or are on carbon rich soils. Across Scotland peat soils store approximately 3 billion tonnes of carbon (Scottish Government, 2022b), with an estimated value of £786 million (Scottish Government, 2021). Restoring and protecting peat soils, and the habitats which sustain them, is therefore a key component of Scotland's drive for net zero. Heath and moorland habitats have further social and economic benefits through water flow regulation, reducing flood risk, and improvements to water quality (Roberts et al., 2023).

To understand the potential impacts of INNS on Scottish heath and moorlands we first present the current state of the research. We then further extend the research to explore the potential impacts of non-native pests and pathogens on heath and moorland habitat plant species.

Methods

Literature review

We conducted a semi-systematic literature review to identify research on heath and moorland invasive species impacts. A four-step search strategy was used:

Step one: Search of published literature for papers on heath and moorland habitats and invasive species, with the search string:

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((ALL=(Peat* OR bog OR fen OR histosol OR "organic soil" OR "moor*" OR "muir*" OR "rush" OR "reed*" OR "heath*")) AND ALL=("invasive species" or "non*native species" or INNS or "alien species" or "introduced species" or "pest species")) AND ALL=(Scotland or Scottish or UK or "Great Britain" or "United Kingdom")
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Step two: Identification of plant pests and pathogens that could be hosted by plants occurring in heath and moorlands through the Defra Plant Health Risk Register (PHRR), downloaded on 12th

INNS in heath and moorland. Roberts and Mitchell. 2024.

October 2023 (Defra, 2023). The data in the PHRR was manipulated to give every combination of pest by host (manipulated PHRR). Host names were split into genera and species because most hosts listed are agricultural varieties or species not the native varieties The data were analysed at host genera level.

To identify the most significant pests for heath and moorland habitats the potentially impacted genera were searched in The National Vegetation Classification (NVC, downloaded 12th October 2023)(Rodwell, 2006), and those that could be hosted by plant genera occurring at more than 25% cover within heathland and mire communities as defined by the NVC were extracted. The list was further refined to those pests and pathogens that had a likelihood of establishment of 4 or 5 after mitigation – that is the highest two levels of likelihood of establishment listed by the PHRR after all possible mitigation to stop their establishment is in place.

Step three: Search of published literature for the plant pests and pathogens identified in Step two. Searches were made in Web of Science for each of the pest or pathogen species names, and refined by heath and moorland habitat if needed:

“Peat* OR bog OR fen OR histosol OR “organic soil” OR "moor*" OR “muir*” OR “rush” OR “reed*” OR “heath*” when large numbers of papers returned.

Step four: Search of InvaCost database (Diagne et al., 2020) for species and heath and moorland habitats.

All searches were combined, and results screened first by title, then abstract and finally full text. Papers were excluded where they did not include either heath or moorland habitats, or impacts of invasive species (e.g., were reporting only on distribution or life history, or limited to discussion of pathways of entry).

Review of impacts

Due to low numbers of papers identified through the initial literature search we also carried out a review of the potential impacts of a decline in host plants in heath and moorlands caused by the plant pests and pathogens identified in Step 2 above. We used expert judgement by author R. Mitchell to identify the impacts of declines in these host species. Impact assessments were made based on the abundance of the genera within heath and moorland communities as listed within the NVC and a visual assessment of plant atlas data (Stroh et al., 2020) to classify genera as:

- Widespread = across most of Scotland,
- moderately widespread = across c half of Scotland,
- Rare – only in c 10 or so one km squares

Assessments were made of the impact of a decline in each of the genera at two levels:

- 50% decline - evenly spread across habitat
- Functional Extinction (FE) where the genera is essentially totally lost, it may exist in small areas but plays no functional role in the ecosystem

All assessments made assuming each genera is impacted by a pest or pathogen in isolation, if one pest or pathogen impacts multiple genera then the impacts could be greater. Impacts are assessed as immediate impacts of loss or decline of plant species.

Results

Literature review

Figure 1 Literature screening

INNS in heath and moorland. Roberts and Mitchell. 2024.

Final papers included 6 ecology papers, one economics and no social papers. Through reviewing full text another invasive moss species was identified (*Campylopus introflexus*), and a further search was carried out for this species in particular.

Summary existing literature

Overall, the number of papers on invasive species in heath and moorlands was limited. This is in line with previous research, where heath and moorland had lowest incidence of alien species in European study (Chytrý et al., 2008). In this study the relatively harsh environment of heath and moorlands was identified as a possible cause, although it should also be noted that heath and moorlands are also less visited and studied overall when compared to landscapes such as agriculture or woodland, and so invasive species may go unnoticed.

A single study on invasive animals was found, following hedgehogs in South Uist. Hedgehogs are native to the Scottish mainland, but invasive to the islands. In South Uist hedgehog densities on heathland were lower than other areas, but still present, and thought to have a negative impact on ground nesting birds (Jackson, 2007).

Rhododendron ponticum was identified as a current invasive species, both itself (Jones et al., 2019) and as a host for *Phytophthora ramorum* and *P. kernoviae* (Drake and Jones, 2017; Purse et al., 2013). In sites cleared of *R. ponticum* shrub growth was higher than uninvaded sites, linked to lower soil pH. Increased in shrub cover led to changes in the structure of the landscape, although it was noted that shrubs were rarer than the grassland in the uninvaded sites, so this may have had a positive impact on landscape heterogeneity (Jones et al., 2019). *R. ponticum* was identified as providing a pathway for *P. ramorum* and *P. kernoviae* to move through moorland habitats, where they might otherwise have been isolated. This was of particular concern in combination with *Vaccinium myrtillus*, which is native to moorland habitats and a known host of *P. kernoviae*, due to the potential for rapid spread (Purse et al., 2013).

Phytophthora ramorum and *Phytophthora kernoviae* are the subject of the only economic study of INNS in heath and moorland. A contingent valuation was carried out valuing reductions in the spread of *P. ramorum* and *P. kernoviae* in heathland, forests, and heritage gardens. Although values for heathland were lower than both forests and heritage gardens, willingness to pay was still estimated at £220m-£647m/year (Drake and Jones, 2017).

The final INNS identified within the literature in peatlands was the bryophyte *Campylopus introflexus*. *C. introflexus* is found everywhere except on the higher mountains within Britain, recorded in 1956 10km squares in Britain between 1990-2013 (British Bryological Society 2020). *C. introflexus* impacts native species composition by forming dense turfs, outcompeting native bryophytes (Essl et al., 2014), and reducing *Calluna* germination, although offset by increased final plant size in greenhouse experiments (Equihua and Usher, 1993). In competing with Sphagnum *C. introflexus* can impact peat formation (Noble et al., 2018), and therefore could have potentially significant impacts on carbon emissions from peat soils. Studies of soil under *C. introflexus* found smaller numbers of ammonifying bacteria and mineral nitrogen assimilating bacteria compared to either native vegetation or bare peat. Fungal communities were also different (Repeckiene et al., 2012).

Potential plant pests and pathogens and the impacts of plant host decline

Due to the lack of existing work on impacts of INNS on heath and moorland we extended our search to include potential impacts of declines in host species on ecosystem services (Appendix 2). In this section we therefore describe the potential impacts of decline in heath and moorland vegetation, such as might be expected by INNS invasions. In general the expected impacts could be applied to any event that led to declines in native heath and moorland plant species, with some specific impacts of INNS in particular also highlighted.

In total there are 310 pests that could be hosted by plant genera occurring at more than 25% cover on Scottish mires and heaths. Of these 49 have a mitigated likelihood of score 4 or 5 the highest two scores (Appendix 1). There are some obvious missing pests on this list such as *Xylella fastidiosa* which know is hosted by *Calluna* (Chapman et al., 2022), but *Calluna* isn't listed as a host in the PHRR. We have not assessed the climatic requirements of the pests listed in Appendix 1 and therefore there is the potential that we have included species that could not survive in Scotland.

We've organised this section by the ecosystem service impacted, and the existing understanding of the costs of impacts. More work is needed to link species to these services, and understand the mechanism by which INNS may impact services. This is not a full valuation and the costs reported here can't be summed to estimate a full cost.

Provisioning services

Biodiversity – maintenance of populations or creation of new varieties

We identified the loss species of genus: *Poa*, *Polygonum*, *Potamogeton*, *Ranunculus*, *Rubus*, *Rumex*, *Salix* as potentially having the largest direct impact on biodiversity if lost as these genera contain a large number of species. Both *Calluna* and *Erica* were not expected to have large direct impacts, as these genera contain few species but their loss or decline may have significant indirect impacts on associated biodiversity due to both genera being used by many species and covering a large land area. *Juniperus* was also highlighted as particularly impactful as one of few native conifers to Scotland.

Maintaining populations ensures that the “option value” of a species persists, that is the species remains available into the future (Humphries et al., 1995). This is linked to the reality that once a species is gone, it is gone, and realisation of its value after the fact will not bring a species back. No specific research we are aware of presents heath and moorland plants option values in particular. However, the current use of some heath and moorland species makes them likely candidates for future option value. Maintaining diverse populations of *Vaccinium*, a genus which includes the blueberry, may provide future fruit breeding options, of particular importance due to climate change (Fielder et al., 2016). Although the Scottish blueberry market is relatively small, with only 241ha grown in Scotland 2023 (Scottish Government, 2023), there is potential for development. At the global scale intra and inter specific differences are important for maintaining diverse populations and therefore important for persistence of habitats (Des Roches et al., 2017; Jump et al., 2009).

Valuing the option value of biodiversity is challenging, because the future use of biodiversity is not known. Some of the valuation is embedded in the other services produced by heath and moorland, and therefore must be cautious to avoid double counting.

Food production

Food production is not the main purpose of the majority of heath and moorland, however the food produced can be particularly valuable to local communities, particularly wild food (Schulp et al., 2014). Grazers are supported by: *Agrostis*, *Anthoxanthum*, *Calluna*, *Deschampsia*, *Festuca*, while honey production utilises *Calluna* and *Erica*. *Bramble*, *Rumex*, *Urtica*, and *Vaccinium* are all directly consumed, although not produced commercially on heath and moorland.

Damage to these species through INNS could therefore have significant economic impacts for local communities. In Caithness and Sutherland agriculture and rough grazing on heath and moorland is estimated to be worth £3.6million/year (Artz et al., 2014), values which rely on the persistence of forage species. Forage species also support game numbers, with a UK value of £12.4 million/year (Schulp et al., 2014).

Vaccinium fruit is often foraged, primarily for private consumption. However, where fruit has been sold it has been priced at between £10-£14/kg. However in this instance production of fruit was not consistent enough to support long-term production (Sanderson and Prendergast, 2002).

Even where not required for food production, use of heath and moorland can increase the value of a good. Heather honey, for example, can fetch a premium price. Previous work has shown heath and moorland have the potential to support 1 hive per 2.6ha, with excess honey production modelled as 9kg/hive. Using market prices the economic benefits of honey produced on peat is estimated at £7/kg, and so £63/hive (MacLennan, 1995). Heather has also been used in production of ale and wine, but in very limited scale (Sanderson and Prendergast, 2002)

Medicine

There is limited knowledge of heath and moorland species used for medicinal purposes. Folklore suggests that *Rumex* (dock leaves) can relieve the pain of stinging nettles, however this is not supported by scientific evidence. *Myrica* has been used for midge repellent, although not a commercial scale (Sanderson and Prendergast, 2002).

Maintenance of biodiversity for its option value for medicine is often suggested, however, as stated above with regards to the value of biodiversity, estimating option values is challenging as eventual use is unknown.

Fibre

Calluna species have been used previously for fibre, although use is not widespread. A small amount of heather is used in thatch, though it's use continues to decline. In 2002 heather for thatch sold for approx. £53/ton (2023 prices) and supported up to 3 jobs in Scotland (Sanderson and Prendergast, 2002), however current use is unknown.

Regulation and maintenance

Soil formation and nutrient cycling

Soil formation is supported by: *Agrostis*, *Anthoxanthum*, *Arctostaphylos*, *Calluna*, *Carex*, *Deschampsia*, *Eleocharis*, *Erica*, *Eriophorum*, *Festuca*, *Juncus*, *Juniperus*, *Lotus*. Much of the understanding of the value of soil formation is related to agricultural production, and therefore not applicable to heath and moorland. Soil formation also supports other services, included water quality, climate regulation through storage of carbon, particularly in peat, and flooding, the costs of which will be considered below.

INNS in heath and moorland. Roberts and Mitchell. 2024.

Pollination

Pollination is supported by a number of heath and moorland plant species. As with soil formation, pollination is typically linked to its impacts on crop yield, which is not applicable within heath and moorland habitats. Pollination also supports honey production, with an estimated value of £63/hive (MacLennan, 1995).

Water quality

A decline in the abundance of *Agrostis*, *Anthoxanthum*, *Arctostaphylos*, *Calluna*, *Carex*, *Deschampsia*, *Eleocharis*, *Erica*, *Eriophorum*, *Festuca*, *Juncus*, *Vaccinium* were all identified as potentially negatively impacting on water quality. These species cover large areas of heath and moorland and if impacted by INNS that cause a rapid decline in their cover could lead to soil erosion and hence a decline in water quality due to sediment load. The extent of this impact would depend on which other plant species replaced the species impacted by the INNS and how quickly this replacement occurred. Water quality in peatland has been valued in previous choice experiments, where willingness to pay to improve peatland from poor to good condition was estimated at £241.90-£304.20/ha and intermediate to good £127.50-£413.90/ha, also including biodiversity and carbon (Glenk and Martin-Ortega, 2018). We might expect similar values for prevention of decline of water quality as a result of INNS damage, where INNS were the primary cause of vegetation loss.

Climate regulation – including carbon sequestration

Carbon storage potential was highest for the species: *Calluna*, *Carex*, *Erica*, *Eriophorum*, *Juncus*. The carbon storage potential of heath and moorlands is significant due to the presence of peat soils. Peat forms a large part of Scotland's drive to net-zero and Scotland's peatlands store approximately 3 billion tonnes of carbon (Scottish Government, 2022b) estimated to be worth £786 million (Scottish Government, 2021). Loss of this carbon due to vegetation loss would therefore be a significant cost, as well as having potentially global impacts.

Erosion control

Species within the genus: *Agrostis*, *Anthoxanthum*, *Arctostaphylos*, *Calluna*, *Carex*, *Dactylis*, *Deschampsia*, *Dryopteris*, *Eleocharis*, *Erica*, *Festuca*, *Iris*, *Juncus*, *Juniperus*, *Salix*, and *Vaccinium* are most abundant within the system. A rapid decline in any of these genera due to damage by invasive pests and pathogens would lead to soil erosion, unless they were rapidly replaced by other species. Because some INNS can prevent plant growth through shading or creating inhospitable environments (e.g., *R. ponticum* lowering soil pH (Jones et al., 2019), native species may also be displaced through invading plant species. Carbon rich soils and peat soils, such as occur under the majority of heaths and moorlands are highly susceptible to erosion where vegetation removed (Rickson et al., 2020).

Costs of erosion have been estimated at the Scottish scale to be £31m/year, but this is not differentiated by soil or land type. In a case study of the Ugie catchment, chosen for containing peatland and moorland, costs of soil erosion were estimated to be £194,861/year, including costs of productivity loss, nutrient loss and sediment removal from canals and rivers (Rickson et al., 2020).

Flood control

An increase in flooding is predicted if species that cover large areas within heathlands, such as species within the genera *Agrostis*, *Anthoxanthum*, *Arctostaphylos*, *Calluna*, *Carex*, *Deschampsia*, *Dryopteris*, *Erica*, *Festuca*, *Iris*, *Juncus*, *Juniperus*, *Myrica*, *Phragmites*, *Poa*, and *Vaccinium* decline due to INNS. This is because vegetation cover will slow down the movement of water through the catchment. Increased flooding has the potential to have significant economic and social impacts.

INNS in heath and moorland. Roberts and Mitchell. 2024.

Insurance costs provide one way that flood costs can be estimated, estimated at £56,776 - £76,035 per household in Scotland (Owusu et al., 2015; Werritty, 2007). Costs of social damage are harder to estimate, but some can be estimated from the Local Authority costs of flood damage, estimated at £259 million/year (SEPA, 2021). However, although biophysical modelling of discharge rates has been developed (Shuttleworth et al., 2019) and the costs of flooding can be estimated, the link between the two data sources has not yet been made.

Cultural

Recreation

Heath and moorland are iconic Scottish landscapes, providing sites for outdoor recreation including hiking, mountain biking and bird watching (Scottish Natural Heritage, 2005), as well as supporting populations of species such as grouse, key in the game shooting industry (Game and Wildlife Conservation Trust, 2015). Species including *Calluna* and *Erica* are particularly important for the quality of the landscape, producing dramatic scenery. Species such as *Rubus* and *Vaccinium* are important for foraging, while *Saxifraga* is of particular botanical interest. Other native species, including *Pteridium* (bracken) can impede access, and so their removal may improve recreation opportunities.

The majority of recreation which occurs on heath and moorland does not incur a direct cost (e.g., there are no entry fees). We therefore rely on peoples stated preferences to estimate value. Golden eagles, iconic species supported by heath and moorland habitats, were estimated to be worth £65 per person per trip (Hanley et al., 2010). Revenue associated to tourism can also be used to estimate the recreation value which may be lost if heath and moorland plant species were lost, with wildlife tourism on moorland is estimated to contribute £138 million to the Scottish economy (Game and Wildlife Conservation Trust, 2015).

Discussion

Overall research on impacts of INNS on heath and moorlands is limited, including both ecological impacts and socioeconomic impacts. In mainland Scotland we found research on only four INNS, with three of those (*R. ponticum*, *P. ramorum* and *P. kernoviae*) tightly linked in their distribution and impacts. Hedgehogs were also studied on South Uist, but have small impacts on a Scottish scale due to being native to the mainland. Similar research on bryophytes, common species within heath and moorlands, follows this trend, with limited research on any invasive bryophyte (Essl et al., 2014). This is at odds with woodlands and forests, where research is more abundant (Haubrock et al., 2021).

Despite the limited current evidence, we do present the potential impacts of introduction of INNS to heath and moorlands through the possible declines in vegetation and impacts of this decline across provisioning, regulating and cultural services. INNS in heath and moorland could have consequences for the coined “Twin Crises” of biodiversity and climate change. Control of INNS is a Key Actions within the Scottish Biodiversity Strategy, as well as a specific action on pathogens “Support surveillance and monitoring to manage pathogens and disease risks” (Scottish Government, 2022a). In addition to specific actions the control of INNS underpins all landscape scale actions with the biodiversity strategy, because INNS have the potential to undermine restoration efforts (Roberts, 2024). Further work into potential invaders, including pests and pathogens, will therefore support biodiversity protection in Scotland, and the aim to be Nature Positive by 2045.

INNS in heath and moorland. Roberts and Mitchell. 2024.

In addition to the biodiversity benefits heath and moorland often include peat soils, and important store of carbon that is currently degraded (Evans et al., 2017). Restoring peat soils, and consequently heath and moorland habitats, is therefore of high importance, and a key component of Scotland's aim for net zero emissions by 2045. With £250 million pledged from the Scottish Government for peatland restoration to 2030 (Forbes, 2020) INNS invasion into heath and moorlands has the potential to significantly impact Scotland's climate change plans.

Limitations

Due to the lack of existing research we have relied on expert judgement to predict the impacts of INNS on heath and moorlands. As a result we are likely to have under or overestimated some impacts, and potentially missed unexpected impacts of plant species decline. We have also not fully captured the cascading effects of a decline in a plant species on wider biodiversity.

The impact is also just assessed for mires and heath and moorlands. The genera considered could be found in other communities where its decline would have a bigger or smaller impact. We have only assessed impacts of pest or pathogens that impact one genera. If the pest or pathogen is hosted by multiple genera then the impacts would be greater and there could be cumulative effects. Finally, impacts will vary depending on the rate at which a species declines, which species replaces the species that are lost, and how quickly this replacement occurs.

Next steps

This work forms part of the Scottish Government Research and Analytical Sciences Division Strategic Research Program 2022-2027 - Identifying the causes of biodiversity change with specific references to the IPBES drivers (JHI-D4-2). The research presented in this report will be used to inform stakeholder interviews and workshops to expand understanding of potential impacts of INNS in heath and moorland habitats, and create a toolkit for estimating ecological, social, and economic impacts.

References

- Artz, R., Donnelly, D., Anderson, R., Mitchell, R., Chapman, S., Smith, P., Cummins, R., Balana, B., Cuthbert, A., 2014. Managing and restoring blanket bog to benefit biodiversity and carbon balance – a scoping study (Commissioned Report No. 562). Scottish Natural Heritage.
- British Bryological Society, 2020, Atlas of British and Irish Bryophytes.
<https://www.britishbryologicalsociety.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/Atlas-of-British-and-Irish-Bryophytes-V2-109.pdf>
- Chapman, D., A'Hara, S., Broadmeadow, S., Cairns, R., Cottrell, J., Fuentes-Montemayor, E., Lester, K., Occhibove, F., Rogerson, S., White, S., Park, K., 2022. Improving knowledge of *Xylella fastidiosa* vector ecology: modelling vector occurrence and abundance in the wider landscape in Scotland: Project Final Report. (No. PHC2020/04). Scotland's Centre of Expertise for Plant Health (PHC).
- Chytrý, M., Maskell, L.C., Pino, J., Pyšek, P., Vilà, M., Font, X., Smart, S.M., 2008. Habitat invasions by alien plants: a quantitative comparison among Mediterranean, subcontinental and oceanic regions of Europe. *J. Appl. Ecol.* 45, 448–458. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2664.2007.01398.x>
- Defra, 2023. Plant Health Risk Register [WWW Document]. URL <https://planthealthportal.defra.gov.uk/pests-and-diseases/uk-plant-health-risk-register/downloadEntireRiskRegister.cfm> (accessed 10.12.23).

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- Des Roches, S., Post, D.M., Turley, N.E., Bailey, J.K., Hendry, A.P., Kinnison, M.T., Schweitzer, J.A., Palkovacs, E.P., 2017. The ecological importance of intraspecific variation. *Nat. Ecol. Evol.* 2, 57–64. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-017-0402-5>
- Diagne, C., Leroy, B., Gozlan, R., Vaissère, A.C., Assailly, C., Nuninger, L., Roiz, D., Jourdain, F., Jaric, I., Courchamp, F., 2020. InvaCost, a public database of the economic costs of biological invasions worldwide. *Sci. Data* 7, 1–12.
- Drake, B., Jones, G., 2017. Public value at risk from *Phytophthora ramorum* and *Phytophthora kernoviae* spread in England and Wales. *J. Environ. Manage.* 191, 136–144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2017.01.013>
- Equihua, M., Usher, M., 1993. Impact of Carpets of the Invasive Moss *Campylopus introflexus* on *Calluna Vulgaris* Regeneration. *J. Ecol.* 81.
- Essl, F., Steinbauer, K., Dullinger, S., Mang, T., Moser, D., 2014. Little, but increasing evidence of impacts by alien bryophytes. *Biol. Invasions* 16, 1175–1184. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-013-0572-2>
- Evans, C., Artz, R., Moxley, J., Taylor, E., Archer, N., Burden, A., Williamson, J., Donnelly, D., Thomson, A., Buys, G., Malcolm, H., Wilson, D., Potts, J., 2017. Implementation of an Emissions Inventory for UK Peatlands.
- Fielder, H., Smith, C., Ford-Lloyd, B., Maxted, N., 2016. Enhancing the conservation of crop wild relatives in Scotland. *J. Nat. Conserv.* 29, 51–61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnc.2015.11.002>
- Forbes, K., 2020. Scottish Budget 2020-2021 statement.
- Game and Wildlife Conservation Trust, 2015. Sustaining Scotland’s Moorland. The role of sporting management in our upland ecosystems. Game & Wildlife Conservation Trust, Perth, Scotland.
- Glenk, K., Martin-Ortega, J., 2018. The economics of peatland restoration. *J. Environ. Econ. Policy* 7, 345–362. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21606544.2018.1434562>
- Hanley, N., Czajkowski, M., Hanley-Nickolls, R., Redpath, S., 2010. Economic values of species management options in human-wildlife conflicts Hen Harriers in Scotland. *Ecol. Econ.*
- Hanley, N., Roberts, M., 2019. The economic benefits of invasive species management. *People Nat.* 1, 124–137. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.31>
- Haubrock, P.J., Turbelin, A.J., Cuthbert, R.N., Novoa, A., Taylor, N.G., Angulo, E., Ballesteros-Mejia, L., Bodey, T.W., Capinha, C., Diagne, C., Essl, F., Golivets, M., Kirichenko, N., Kourantidou, M., Leroy, B., Renault, D., Verbrugge, L., Courchamp, F., 2021. Economic costs of invasive alien species across Europe. *NeoBiota* 67, 153–190. <https://doi.org/10.3897/neobiota.67.58196>
- Humphries, C., Williams, P., Vane-Wright, R., 1995. Measuring biodiversity value for conservation. *Annu. Rev. Ecol. Syst.* 26, 93–111.
- IPBES, 2019. Models of drivers of biodiversity and ecosystem change [WWW Document]. Work Programme 2030. URL <https://www.ipbes.net/models-drivers-biodiversity-ecosystem-change> (accessed 2.27.24).
- Jackson, D.B., 2007. Factors affecting the abundance of introduced hedgehogs (*Erinaceus europaeus*) to the Hebridean island of South Uist in the absence of natural predators and implications for nesting birds. *J. Zool.* 271, 210–217. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-7998.2006.00204.x>
- Jones, G.L., Tomlinson, M., Owen, R., Scullion, J., Winters, A., Jenkins, T., Ratcliffe, J., Gwynn-Jones, D., 2019. Shrub establishment favoured and grass dominance reduced in acid heath grassland systems cleared of invasive *Rhododendron ponticum*. *Sci. Rep.* 9, 2239. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-38573-z>
- Jump, A.S., Marchant, R., Peñuelas, J., 2009. Environmental change and the option value of genetic diversity. *Trends Plant Sci.* 14, 51–58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tplants.2008.10.002>
- MacLennan, A., 1995. Honey Production from heather moor in Scotland, in: Thompson, D., Hester, A., Usher, M. (Eds.), *Heather and Moorland: Cultural Landscapes*. HMSO, Edinburgh, pp. 95–101.

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- Mitchell, R.J., 2022. Identification of habitats at greatest risk from plant pestspathogens - case study_published.pdf.
- Mooney, H.A., 2001. Invasive alien species - The nature of the problem. Assessment and management of alien species that threaten ecosystems, habitat and species. Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity, Montreal, Canada.
- Noble, A., Palmer, S.M., Glaves, D.J., Crowle, A., Brown, L.E., Holden, J., 2018. Prescribed burning, atmospheric pollution and grazing effects on peatland vegetation composition. *J. Appl. Ecol.* 55, 559–569. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12994>
- Owusu, S., Wright, G., Arthur, S., 2015. Public attitudes towards flooding and property-level flood protection measures. *Nat. Hazards* 77, 1963–1978. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-015-1686-x>
- Purse, B.V., Graeser, P., Searle, K., Edwards, C., Harris, C., 2013. Challenges in predicting invasive reservoir hosts of emerging pathogens: mapping *Rhododendron ponticum* as a foliar host for *Phytophthora ramorum* and *Phytophthora kernoviae* in the UK. *Biol. Invasions* 15, 529–545. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-012-0305-y>
- Repeckiene, J., Salina, O., Jukoniene, I., 2012. Microbial communities in disturbed peatlands colonized with invasive moss *Campylopus introflexus* (Hedw.) Brid. *Pol. J. Ecol.*
- Rickson, Deeks, Graves, Hannam, Keay, Lilly, Baggaley, 2020. Developing a method to estimate the costs of soil erosion in high-risk Scottish catchments: Final Report (No. UCR/004/18 CRF CR/2015/15).
- Roberts, M., 2024. Framework for costing the Scottish Biodiversity Strategy (SEFARI report for Scottish Government).
- Roberts, M., Mzek, T., Koseoglu, N., Parker, T., Artz, R., 2023. Scottish peat values and ecosystem services: Evidence Map of literature (RESAS). James Hutton Institute.
- Rodwell, J., 2006. NVC Users Handbook [WWW Document]. URL <https://hub.jncc.gov.uk/assets/a407ebfc-2859-49cf-9710-1bde9c8e28c7#NVC-floristic-tables.xls> (accessed 10.12.23).
- Sanderson, H., Prendergast, H., 2002. Commercial uses of wild and traditionally managed plants in England and Scotland. Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew.
- Schulp, C.J.E., Thuiller, W., Verburg, P.H., 2014. Wild food in Europe: A synthesis of knowledge and data of terrestrial wild food as an ecosystem service. *Ecol. Econ.* 105, 292–305. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2014.06.018>
- Scottish Government, 2023. Agricultural Census 2023.
- Scottish Government, 2022a. Scottish Biodiversity Strategy to 2045. Tackling the Nature Emergency in Scotland.
- Scottish Government, 2022b. Scottish Natural Capital Accounts: 2022 (Official Statistics publication for Scotland - Experimental Statistics).
- Scottish Government, 2021. Scottish natural capital accounts: 2021, Official Statistics publication for Scotland.
- Scottish Natural Heritage, 2005. The Peatlands of Caithness and Sutherland. Management Strategy 2005-2015. Life Peatlands Project.
- SEPA, 2021. Flood Risk Management Plans [WWW Document]. Straegic Environ. Assess. URL <https://www2.sepa.org.uk/frmplans/> (accessed 1.22.23).
- Shuttleworth, E.L., Evans, M.G., Pilkington, M., Spencer, T., Walker, J., Milledge, D., Allott, T.E.H., 2019. Restoration of blanket peat moorland delays stormflow from hillslopes and reduces peak discharge. *J. Hydrol. X* 2, 100006. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hydroa.2018.100006>
- Stroh, P., Walker, K., Humphrey, T., Prescott, O., Burkmar, R., 2020. Plant Atlas 2020 [WWW Document]. URL <https://plantatlas2020.org/atlas/2cd4p9h.w5z> (accessed 10.12.23).
- Werritty, A., 2007. Exploring the social impacts of flood risk and flooding in Scotland. Scottish Executive Social Research, Edinburgh.

Appendix 1: Plant pests and pathogens that are listed in the Defra plant health risk register with a mitigated likelihood of establishment of 4 or 5 that could be hosted by plant genera that occur on heathlands, moors and peatland.

Pest	Common name or abbreviation	Type of pest	Likelihood mitigated
<i>Agrilus fleischeri</i>		Insect	4
Blueberry shoestring sobemovirus		Virus or Viroid	4
<i>Calamobius filum</i>	Grain borer	Insect	4
<i>Callidiellum rufipenne</i>	Cedar long-horned beetle; Cedar longhorn beetle; Japanese cedar longhorn beetle; small cedar longhorn beetle	Insect	4
<i>Cathaica fasciola</i>		Other	4
<i>Ceroplastes japonicus</i>	Tortoise wax scale	Insect	4
<i>Chrysodeixis chalcites</i>	Golden twin spot; Green garden looper; Groundnut semilooper; Tomato looper	Insect	4
<i>Cinara curvipes</i>	Balsam fir aphid; Puceron du sapin (French)	Insect	4
<i>Colletotrichum boninense</i>		Fungus	4
<i>Disonychia conjugata</i>		Insect	4
<i>Duponchelia fovealis</i>	Dark Marbled Tabby; European Pepper Moth; Southern European marshland pyralid	Insect	4
<i>Eotetranychus sexmaculatus</i>	Citrus spider mite; Six spotted spider mite	Mite	4
<i>Erthesina fullo</i>	Yellow-spotted stink bug	Insect	4
<i>Eucarazzia elegans</i>	Elegant aphid	Insect	4
<i>Euzophera bigella</i>	Fruit; pyralid; quince moth	Insect	4
<i>Globodera pallida</i> European Strains	Cyst nematode; Pale potato cyst nematode; Potato cyst nematode; White potato cyst nematode	Nematode	4
<i>Globodera rostochiensis</i> European Strains	Cyst nematode; Golden nematode; Golden potato cyst nematode; Nematode; potato cyst; Potato cyst nematode; Root nematode	Nematode	4
<i>Gnomoniopsis idaeicola</i> (P. Karst.) D.M. Walker - All Hosts		Fungus	4
Grapevine Syrah virus 1		Virus or Viroid	4
<i>Gymnosporangium tremelloides</i>	Rust: apple; Stem gall: Juniperus spp.	Fungus	4
<i>Halyomorpha halys</i>	brown marmorated stink bug; Yellow-Brown stink bug	Insect	4

Pest	Common name or abbreviation	Type of pest	Likelihood mitigated
Iris yellow spot virus		Virus or Viroid	5
Lamprodila festiva		Insect	5
Lonsdalea populi		Bacterium	4
Luperomorpha xanthodera	Rose Flea beetle	Insect	4
Musotima nitidalis		Insect	4
Neofusicoccum luteum		Fungus	5
Phenacoccus solani		Insect	4
Phytophthora bisheria		Oomycete	5
Phytophthora ramorum	Ramorum leaf blight; Ramorum shoot dieback; Rhododendron twig blight; Sudden oak death	Oomycete	4
Planococcus vovae	Nassonov's mealybug	Insect	4
Plantago asiatica mosaic virus		Virus or Viroid	5
Platynota idaeusalis	Tufted apple bud moth	Insect	4
Platynota stultana	Omnivorous leafroller	Insect	4
Pochazia shantungensis	Brown winged cicada	Insect	4
Popillia japonica	Japanese beetle	Insect	4
Pratylenchus scribneri	Root lesion nematode	Nematode	4
Prunus necrotic ringspot virus	Almond bud failure; Almond calico; Almond line pattern; Almond necrotic ringspot; Apricot line pattern; Apricot necrotic ringspot; Cherry lace leaf; Cherry line pattern; Cherry necrotic ringspot; Cherry ringspot; Cherry rugose mosaic; Cherry stecklenberge	Virus or Viroid	4
Rhopalosiphum nymphaeae	Water-lily aphid	Insect	4
Scutellonema brachyurus		Nematode	5
Siphonotrophia cupressi		Insect	4
Sphaerolecanium prunastri	globose scale; plum lecanium	Insect	4
Takahashia japonica	String cottony scale	Insect	4
Thekopsora minima	leaf rust of blueberry	Fungus	4
Thrips setosus		Insect	4
Tobacco ringspot virus	bud blight of soybean; Tobacco ringspot virus 1; Tobacco ringspot virus: tobacco; soybean	Virus or Viroid	4
Tomato chlorosis virus		Virus or Viroid	4

Pest	Common name or abbreviation	Type of pest	Likelihood mitigated
Xiphinema index	Californian dagger nematode; Dagger nematode; Fan-leaf virus nematode	Nematode	5
Xylosandrus germanus	Black timber bark beetle; Smaller alnus bark beetle; tea root borer	Insect	4

Appendix 2: The plant hosts, by genera, that occur in Scottish heathlands and mires at more than 25% cover and host pests and pathogens that are listed in Defra's plant health risk register with a mitigated likelihood of establishment of 4 or 5 (the highest two values).

Host genera	Number of pests in the risk register with a mitigated likelihood of 4 or 5
Achillea	6
Agrostis	8
Anthoxanthum	2
Arctostaphylos	6
Calluna	2
Caltha	1
Cardamine	3
Carex	3
Dactylis	6
Deschampsia	1
Dryopteris	1
Eleocharis	1
Erica	2
Eriophorum	1
Eupatorium	6
Festuca	6
Galium	2
Genista	1
Geum	2
Iris	12
Juncus	3
Juniperus	51
Lotus	2
Lycopus	1
Mentha	22
Myosotis	2
Myrica	7
Osmunda	1

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Phragmites	4
Plantago	12
Poa	11
Polygonum	11
Potamogeton	1
Prunella	1
Pteridium	1
Ranunculus	7
Rubus	157
Rumex	13
Salix	101
Saxifraga	2
Senecio	17
Thymus	6
Trollius	1
Urtica	11
Vaccinium	110
Valeriana	2
Vicia	35
Viola	6